

An Delphi Application for the Syntactic and Lexical Analysis of a Phrase Using Cocke, Younger, and Kasami Algorithm

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Abstract

This paper focus on the Cocke, Younger, and Kasami algorithm. We present a Delphi application that analyzies the lexicon and the syntax of a sentence in Romanian. We use a Chomsky normal form (CNF) grammar. We will present the source of a Delphi implementation of the CKY algorithm.

Keywords: CKY algorithm, lexical analysis, Delphi programming

1. General presentation

The program, which is highly complex, is part of the category of natural language processing programs. A phrase is entered into a text box and the program tells whether the phrase is correct or not, according to some *vocabulary* and an array of previously established *syntactic rules* which make up a certain *grammar* [1].

	orice	barbat	iubeste	o	femeie	frumoasa	si	desteapta
0	{Det}	{NP}			{S}	{S}		{S}
1		{N,NP}			{S}	{S}		{S}
2			{V}		{VP}	{VP}		{VP}
3				{Det}	{NP}	{NP}		{NP}
4					{N,NP}	{NP}		{NP}
5						{A,AP}		{AP}
6							{C}	{CP}
7								{A,AP}

Figure 1. Example of parsing the phrase “orice barbat iubeste o femeie frumoasa si desteapta” (“any man loves a beautiful and intelligent woman”)

For example, in the figure above (Figure 1), the phrase “orice barbat iubeste o femeie frumoasa si desteapta” (“any man loves a beautiful and intelligent woman”) has been entered and has been accepted as correct. The table shows the diagram of the syntactic analysis for the phrase,

which starts from the row labelled with “0” and ends with the column labelled “desteapta” (“intelligent”).

The lexicon used in the analysis, written in the 'LEX.TXT' text file, was the following:

```
Det->orice
Det->fiecare
Det->o
Det->un
Pron->el
N->barbat
N->femeie
V->iubeste
V->uraste
A->frumoasa
A->desteapta
C->si
C->sau
```

Thus, the previously analysed phrase contains words only from the chosen vocabulary. On the other hand, the phrase "any dog hates a cat ", although syntactically correct in Romanian, is not accepted because it contains words that have not been entered into our vocabulary.

The file contains, on each row, a rule of the type (2):

$$GM \rightarrow W \quad (2)$$

where GM is a grammatical category (or part of speech) and W is a word from a certain dictionary.

Syntax rules (from the 'GRAM.TXT' file) constitute a subset of the Romanian syntax rules:

```
S->NP VP
NP->Pron
NP->N
NP->Det N
NP->NP AP
AP->A
AP->AP CP
CA->C A
VP->V VP
VP->V NP
```

Thus, by using the established notation (S = sentence, NP = noun phrase, VP = verb phrase, N = noun, Det = determiner (article), AP = adjectival phrase, A = adjective, C = conjunction, V = verb, CA = group made up of a conjunction and an adjective.

The syntax rules are given, one on each line, thus (3):

$$GM1 \rightarrow GM2 GM3 \quad (3)$$

meaning that the first grammatical category (GM1) forms out of the concatenation of the other two (GM2 and GM3), from the right side of the arrow.

According to the syntax rules used in our application, the phrase we have analysed in the beginning is correct, while the following figure (Figure 2) presents a case viewed as incorrect.

Figure 2. A rejected "sentence"

We should mention the fact that the algorithm that we have implemented uses only grammars written in Chomsky (CNF) normal format. A CNF grammar is a context-free grammar where productions take the form of: $A \rightarrow B C$, where A is a non-terminal, and B and C are non-terminals or pre-terminals [1], [5]. We have also considered rules of the type $A \rightarrow B$ as acceptable. Therefore, in the right side of the production rules there will be two or only one element.

Details concerning the topic under discussion, for the unknowing reader, can be studied in the works mentioned as references.

2. The Cocke, Younger, and Kasami Algorithm

We will further present the basic analysis algorithm (also called "chart-parsing") elaborated by Cocke, Younger, and Kasami and named the basic *CYK algorithm* [2], [5]

The algorithm uses a matrix (a diagram) chart, like those in the previous figures.

First of all, we need certain definitions:

The following operation is defined (4):

$$\text{Star}(X,Y)=\{C|(A \in X) \wedge (B \in Y) \wedge (C \rightarrow AB \in \text{Rules})\} \quad (4)$$

where *Rules* denotes the production rules of the grammar.

This represents the fact that the product of two cells from the matrix is created by combining all the pairs of items in the two cells which satisfy certain grammar rules.

Another operation that is defined is (5):

$$\text{Closure}(S) = \{A|(A \in S) \vee ((B \in \text{Closure}(S)) \wedge (A \rightarrow B \in \text{Rules}))\} \quad (5)$$

This represents the fact that closing an S cell is formed of the content of S plus the result of adding any other category deriving from an existing member of S 's closure. For example, if N is in S then N belongs to $\text{Closure}(S)$; then, if there is a rule $\text{NP} \rightarrow N$, and NP will be added to $\text{Closure}(S)$; things continue thus as long as new members can still be added to $\text{Closure}(S)$.

Finally, there is also a Lookup function, of the type (6):

$$\text{Lookup}(k) = \{A|A \rightarrow \text{word}_k\} \quad (6),$$

meaning that it gives us the list of grammatical categories that the word number k from our phrase provides (sometimes a word can have more than one grammatical category, for example “going” can be both a noun or a verb).

Taking into consideration the above definitions, the basic CKY algorithm is [4]:

```

for k:=1 to n do
begin
  chart[k-1,k]:=Closure(Lookup(k));
  for i:=k-2 downto 0 do
  begin
    chart[i,k]:=∅;
    for j:=k-1 downto i+1 do
    chart[i,k]:=chart[i,k] ∪ Star(chart[i,j],chart[j,k]);
    chart[i,k]:=Closure(chart[i,k]);
  end
end;
if S ∈ chart[0,n] then Accept else Reject

```

The algorithm presented above will be implemented into the following program where, due to some restrictions of the Pascal language, procedures for the three defined functions will be realized.

3. Implementing the algorithm

unit parser1;

interface

uses

Windows, Messages, SysUtils, Classes, Graphics,
Controls, Forms, Dialogs, StdCtrls, Grids, ExtCtrls;

type

```

TForm1 = class(TForm)
  StringGrid1: TStringGrid;
  Edit1: TEdit;
  Label1: TLabel;
  procedure Edit1KeyPress(Sender: TObject; var Key: Char);
  procedure FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
private
  { Private declarations }
public
  { Public declarations }
end;

```

var

Form1: TForm1;

implementation

```

{$R *.DFM}
const max=20; maxreg=20; maxcuv=5; maxcuvinte=20;

```

In order to memorize the elements displayed to the left and to the right of a grammar rule, we use the type Word.

```

type Cuvint=String[30];
  MultimeDeCuvinte=object
    nc: Integer;
    cuv: array[1..maxcuv] of Cuvint;
    procedure Adauga(c: Cuvint);
  end;

```

A rule is made up of two parts, one to the left and one to the right, and a grammar is made up of several of such rules.

```
regula=record
    st,dr: Cuvint
end;

type Gramatica=object
    nr: Integer;
    reg: array[1..maxreg] of regula;
    procedure Citeste(nf: String);
end;
```

The diagram is a matrix where each cell is a set of words. G is the grammar with the rules and D is actually the word dictionary used.

```
var chart:array[0..max, 0..max] of MultimeDeCuvinte;
    G: Gramatica;
    D: Gramatica;
    Propoz: array[1..maxcuvinte] of Cuvint;
```

Drawing the diagram is done according to the content of the chart matrix by using the StringGrid1 control [3]:

```
procedure DeseneazaChart(i,j: Integer);
var t: String; k,kk: Integer;
begin
    if chart[i,j].nc>=1 then
        begin
            t:='{';
            for k:=1 to chart[i,j].nc-1 do
                t:=t+chart[i,j].cuv[k]+' ';
                t:=t+chart[i,j].cuv[chart[i,j].nc]+'}';
                Form1.StringGrid1.Cells[j,i+1]:=t;
                Form1.StringGrid1.Refresh
            end
        end
    end;
```

The following function checks whether a given word x is or is not inside a set of words M .

```
function EsteIn(x: Cuvint; M: MultimeDeCuvinte): Boolean;
var este: Boolean; i: Integer;
begin
    este:=False;
    for i:=1 to M.nc do
        if x=M.cuv[i] then este:=True;
        EsteIn:=este
    end;
```

For objects of the type MultimeDeCuvinte (SetOfWords) we have provided a procedure for adding a new word:

```
procedure MultimeDeCuvinte.Adauga(c: Cuvint);
begin
    nc:=nc+1; cuv[nc]:=c
end;
```

Based on the last two subprograms described, we can define `Star`, `Closure` and `Lookup` operations, as well as the operation of reading a grammar whose rules are written in a given text file.

```
procedure Star(X,Y: MultimeDeCuvinte;  
var Z: MultimeDeCuvinte);  
var i,j,k: Integer;  
begin  
    Z.nc:=0;  
    for i:=1 to X.nc do  
        for j:=1 to Y.nc do  
            for k:=1 to G.nr do  
                if G.reg[k].dr=X.cuv[i]+' '+Y.cuv[j] then  
                    Z.Adauga(G.reg[k].st)  
            end;  
        end;  
    end;  
end;
```

```
procedure Closure(S: MultimeDeCuvinte;  
var C: MultimeDeCuvinte);  
var i: Integer; gata: Boolean;  
begin  
    C:=S;  
    repeat  
        gata:=True;  
        for i:=1 to G.nr do  
            if EsteIn(G.reg[i].dr,C) then  
                if not EsteIn(G.reg[i].st,C) then  
                    begin  
                        C.Adauga(G.reg[i].st);  
                        gata:=False  
                    end  
                end;  
        until gata  
    end;  
end;
```

```
procedure Gramatica.Citeste(nf: String);  
var f: TextFile; s: String; p: Byte;  
begin  
    nr:=0;  
    AssignFile(f,nf);  
    Reset(f);  
    while not eof(f) do  
        begin  
            nr:=nr+1;  
            ReadLn(f,s);  
            p:=Pos('->',s);  
            reg[nr].st:=Copy(s,1,p-1);  
            reg[nr].dr:=Copy(s,p+2,Length(s)-(p+1))  
        end;  
    CloseFile(f)  
end;
```

```
procedure Lookup(k: Integer; var L: MultimeDeCuvinte);  
var i: Integer;  
begin  
    L.nc:=0;  
    for i:=1 to D.nr do  
        if D.reg[i].dr=Propoz[k] then  
            begin  
                L.nc:=L.nc+1;  
                L.cuv[L.nc]:=D.reg[i].st  
            end  
        end;  
end;
```

Finally, the following procedure performs the grammatical analysis of the given phrase (ss), on the basis of the algorithm that has been theoretically described in the first paragraph.

```
procedure Parseaza(ss: String);
var i,j,k,kk: Integer;
    n: Integer; p: Byte;
    L,C,S: MultimeDeCuvinte; t: String;
begin
    ss:=ss+' ';
    n:=0;
    while ss<>' ' do
        begin
            p:=Pos(' ',ss);
            n:=n+1;
            Propoz[n]:=Copy(ss,1,p-1);
            Form1.StringGrid1.Cells[n,0]:=Propoz[n];
            Str(n-1,t);
            Form1.StringGrid1.Cells[0,n]:=t;
            Delete(ss,1,p)
        end;
    Form1.StringGrid1.RowCount:=1+n;
    Form1.StringGrid1.ColCount:=1+n;
    Form1.StringGrid1.Show;
    for k:=1 to n do
        begin
            Lookup(k,L);
            Closure(L,C);
            chart[k-1,k]:=C;
            for i:=k-2 downto 0 do
                begin
                    chart[i,k].nc:=0;
                    for j:=k-1 downto i+1 do
                        begin
                            Star(chart[i,j],chart[j,k],S);
                            for kk:=1 to S.nc do
                                if not EsteIn(S.cuv[kk],chart[i,k]) then
                                    chart[i,k].Adauga(S.cuv[kk])
                            end;
                        end;
                    Closure(chart[i,k],C); chart[i,k]:=C
                end
            end;
        for i:=0 to n do
            for j:=0 to n do DeseneazaChart(i,j);
                if EsteIn('S',chart[0,n]) then
                    Form1.Label1.Caption:= 'Fraza acceptata.'
                else
                    Form1.Label1.Caption:= 'Fraza rejectata.'
            end;
        end;
procedure TForm1.Edit1KeyPress(Sender: TObject; var Key: Char);
begin
    if Key=Chr(13) then Parseaza(Edit1.Text)
end;

procedure TForm1.FormCreate(Sender: TObject);
begin
    Caption:='Basic CKY Parser'; StringGrid1.Hide;
    G.Citeste('gram.txt'); D.Citeste('lex.txt');
end;

end.
```

Bellow are the contents of the two files (grammmnar and dictionary) that we have used in the examples we have analysed:

GRAM.TXT

S->NP VP
NP->Pron
NP->N
NP->Det N
NP->NP AP
AP->A
AP->AP CP
CP->C A
VP->V VP
VP->V NP

LEX.TXT

Det->orice
Det->fiecare
Det->o
Det->un
Pron->el
N->barbat
N->femeie
V->iubeste
V->uraste
A->frumoasa
A->desteapta
C->si
C->sau

We should mention the fact that the algorithm works only if there are at least two symbols in the right side of each grammar rule, therefore we should pay due attention to rewriting the grammars that we use, so that they may meet with this restriction.

Conclusion

We described in this paper the CKY algorithm that can be applied for lexical and syntactical analysis of Romanian sentences, if we write the grammar as a CNF grammar. Also, we implemented the algorithm in Delphi 3.0, developed by Borland (www.borland.com).

References:

- [1] Chomsky, N. (1965). *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. Boston, MA: MIT Press, ISBN 0-262-53007-4.
- [2] Hopcroft, J. E., Motwani, R., Ullman, J. D. (2006). *Introduction to Automata Theory, Languages, and Computation*, 3rd Edition, Addison-Wesley, ISBN 0-321-45536-3, p 272.
- [3] Kreylos, O., ECS 12- Lesson 11 – Chomsky Normal Form, Retrieved from <http://www.enseignement.polytechnique.fr/informatique/profs/Luc.Marandet/IF/09/chomsky.pdf>
- [4] Patrut, B. (2006). *20 Applications in Delphi and Visual Basic*. Bacău, Romania: EduSoft, (in Romanian).
- [5] Sipser, M. (1997), *Introduction to the Theory of Computation* (1st ed.). IPS, p. 99, ISBN 0-534-94728-X.